

Physico-Chemical Studies of Complex Formation Between Uranyl Ion and 5-Hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone

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5-Hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone forms an orange-coloured, water-soluble complex with uranyl ions. The complex has been studied in aqueous ethanol by spectrophotometric, potentiometric, and conductometric methods. These studies reveal that the complex molecule contains uranium and 5-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone in the ratio of 1:2. The complex obeys Beer's law. A method for spectrophotometric determination of traces of uranium has been developed.

Uranium has been reported to form complexes with several flavones such as quercetin¹, morin²⁻⁴, and galangin⁵. Compositions of these complexes have been deduced from spectrophotometric studies and methods for the estimation of this metal have been developed. It has now been found that 5-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone forms a stable, orange-coloured complex with uranium. The complex has been studied by spectrophotometric, potentiometric, and conductometric methods in aqueous ethanol medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Uranyl nitrate (A.R., B.D.H.) was used for preparing standard solutions ($M/1,000$) of uranium. Uranium concentration was determined gravimetrically by precipitating with oxine. An ethanolic solution of 5-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone containing 0.298 g./litre ($M/1,000$) was prepared.

The absorption spectrum of the flavone was taken, using a Perkin-Elmer spectracord. All other spectrophotometric observations were taken, using a Coleman spectrophotometer, model No. 14. All pH and E.M.F. measurements were made with the help of a Metrohm pH-meter, type-E-350. A circular slide wire conductivity bridge (Leeds & Northrup) was used for conductivity measurements.

Spectrophotometric Studies

Absorption Spectra.—The absorption spectrum of the flavone was taken in the ultraviolet as well as in the visible region. Maximum absorption by the flavone was observed at 277 m μ (Fig. 1, curve A). No absorption maximum was observed in the visible

1. Kommdenda, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 531.
2. Beck and Hantos, *Magyar Kem. Foly.*, 1954, 60, 244.
3. Almaasy *et al.*, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1955, 7, 317.
4. Beck and Hantos, *ibid.*, 1955, 8, 233.
5. Katyal and Singh, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 885.

region. The absorption spectra of the complex were studied at various pH values (from 3.0 to 5.0) and the maximum was always found at 420 m μ (Fig. 1, curve B). The wave length 420 m μ was consequently selected for further investigations. At higher pH values, turbidity began to appear after keeping the complex solution for some time. The molar ratio of the flavone to uranium was maintained at 5 while preparing the solutions for spectra. One ml of uranyl solution was mixed with 5 ml of the flavone solution and the mixture was diluted to 25.0 ml, maintaining 40% ethanolic medium. These conditions were kept constant in subsequent studies.

FIG. 1 Absorption spectra.

A: 5-Hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone using EtOH as blank.

B: Uranyl-5-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavone complex using flavone as blank; pH 3.75.

Effect of Acidity.—The effect of acidity on the complex was studied and the maximum absorption was observed at pH 5.0. At still higher pH values, a slight turbidity appeared due probably to the tendency of uranyl ions to combine with hydroxyl ions. The pH adjustments were made by the addition of a very dilute solution of NaOH or HCl.

Stability of the Complex.—The complex was found to be quite stable and no change in colour intensity was noticed even after keeping the solution of the complex overnight at room temperature.

Beer-Lambert's Law.—The complex obeys Beer-Lambert's law from 1 to 15 p.p.m. of uranium concentration and the method can thus conveniently be used for spectrophotometric estimation of uranium.

Composition of the Complex

Job's modified method^{6,7} was used for determination of composition of the complex. The peak in the curve (Fig. 2) occurred when the molar ratio of the flavone to uranyl ion was 6.6: 3.4, i.e., 2:1 (approx.).

The composition was also verified by the slope-ratio method⁸. For this purpose, two series of solutions were prepared, using $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solutions of the flavone and uranium. In one series, uranium concentration was varied, maintaining the flavone concentration constant and in sufficient excess; in the other series, the flavone concentration was varied, maintaining uranium concentration constant and in sufficient excess. The optical densities of the solutions of both series were determined at 420 m μ , using 40% ethanol as reference. The values obtained were plotted and the curves M and R (Fig. 3) were obtained.

FIG. 2. Composition by Job's method. x ml flavone ($M/1000$) added to $(10-x)$ ml of uranyl soln. ($M/1000$). x varied from 1 to 9; total vol. = 25 ml.

FIG. 3. Composition by slope-ratio method. M: $M/1000$ uranyl soln. (0.5-2.5 ml) added to $M/1000$ flavone (5 ml); total vol. 25 ml in 4% EtOH. R: $M/1000$ flavone (0.5 to 5 ml) added to 5 ml of uranyl soln. under same conditions.

From the slopes of the two curves, it is evident that the composition of the complex is UO_2X_2 , where X is a molecule of flavone. The following tentative structure can thus be suggested for the complex:

6. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **2**, 9, 113.

7. Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 497.

8. Harvey and Manning, *ibid.*, 1955, **77**, 4488.

Potentiometric Studies

Fig. 4 shows titration curve (A) of flavone against uranyl salt solution. Both the solutions were prepared in 40% ethanol medium. The curve shows that E.M.F. of the flavone solution goes on decreasing with the addition of uranyl nitrate solution. When one equivalent of uranyl nitrate solution has been added to two equivalents of the flavone, pH becomes nearly constant, showing the formation of 1:2 complex in the system. Curve B shows E.M.F. changes of only uranyl nitrate solution at similar concentrations. The curve A lies below B showing that there is an increase in hydrogen-ion concentration in the solution, which is only possible by the liberation of hydrogen ions during complex formation. As two equivalents of the flavone are utilised for one equivalent of the uranyl ion for formation of the complex (curve A), the reaction may be represented as

FIG. 4. Potentiometric titration.
Curve A: 10 ml of $M/2,500$ flavone in 40% EtOH.
B: 10 ml of 40% EtOH.

FIG. 5. Conductometric titration,

Conductometric Studies

Fig. 5 shows titration curve of flavone solution against a solution of uranyl nitrate. The conductance of the solution goes on increasing till one equivalent of the uranyl solution has been added to two equivalents of the flavone. The rise in conductance is explained to be due to liberation of hydrogen ions during formation of the complex. After this, addition of more of uranyl nitrate solution enhances the conductance due to the conducting nature of the component ions. The break in the curve again shows the formation of 1:2 complex.

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